

Mortgage Interest Rates

April 28, 2026

1 Description

BankOnYourBlock, a leading financial institution, determines mortgage interest rates based on applicants' default risk, charging higher rates for high-risk individuals.

1) **BankOnYourBlock relies on employees to assess a client's risk of non-payment.**

- a) Imagine you are a client of BankOnYourBlock. How acceptable do you find it when an employee assesses the risk of non-payment?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- b) Please describe a situation where using employees would be beneficial for assessing the risk of non-payment.
- c) Please describe a situation where using employees would be harmful for assessing the risk of non-payment

InsureYou, an insurance company, collects data on past mortgage applicants from minority demographic groups, including education, dependents, marital status, income, mortgage amount, credit history, outstanding debt, savings, investments, collateral, and employment stability. InsureYou uses the collected data to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict whether an applicant will default.

2) **Instead of employees, the BankOnYourBlock now relies on InsureYou's AI to assess a client's risk of non-payment.**

- a) Imagine you are a client of BankOnYourBlock. How acceptable do you find it when an AI assesses the risk of non-payment?
 - i) completely unacceptable

- ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be beneficial for assessing the risk of non-payment.
 - Please describe a situation where using the AI would be harmful for assessing the risk of non-payment.

3) **Consider that BankOnYourBlock relies on InsureYou’s AI to assess a client’s risk of non-payment and calculate their interest rates. InsureYou identified an issue with its AI where it offers lower interest rates to brunettes over non-brunettes, even if they have a high risk. To address this, InsureYou modifies the AI to mitigate the issue.**

- Please describe how ‘the AI modification’ could be beneficial for everyone.

Modifying the AI has some side effects, which are described as different scenarios in parts (a), (b), (c) and (d). Please indicate your preference for the following scenarios:

- a) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that it incorrectly predicts higher interest rates for low risk applicants. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still provide correct interest rates for low risk applicants. In this scenario, if you were a client, which option would you suggest for InsureYou to choose?**
 - i) The AI strongly favors brunettes; otherwise, it provides the correct interest rates.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it provides slightly incorrect interest rates.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it provides moderately incorrect interest rates.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it provides highly incorrect interest rates
 - Give an example of potential issues if InsureYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- b) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that BankOnYourBlock can learn whether a client belongs to a minority demographic group by identifying if they were part of InsureYou’s data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still prevent BankOnYourBlock**

from identifying a client belongs to a minority demographic group. In this scenario, if you were a client, which option would you suggest for InsureYou to choose?

- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal whether the applicant belongs to a minority demographic group.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal whether the applicant belongs to a minority demographic group.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal whether the applicant belongs to a minority demographic group.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal whether the applicant belongs to a minority demographic group.
- Give an example of potential issues if InsureYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- c) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that BankOnYourBlock can now determine the number of women in InsureYou's data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still protect the information about the number of women. In this scenario, if you were a client, which option would you suggest for InsureYou to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
- Give an example of potential issues if InsureYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- d) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that BankOnYourBlock's employees could exploit the AI to disadvantage blue-eyed applicants by giving them a higher interest rates. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and protect the AI from manipulation. In this scenario, if you were a client, which option would you suggest for InsureYou to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it is highly difficult to manipulate.

- ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it is moderately difficult to manipulate.
- iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it is slightly difficult to manipulate.
- iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it is not difficult to manipulate.
 - Give an example of potential issues if InsureYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

2 Demographic Information

- 1) What is your gender?
 - Man | Woman | Non-Binary | Prefer not to answer | Self-describe [text input]
- 2) Do you identify as being part of any minority groups?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 3) What age group do you belong to?
 - 18-25 | 26-35 | 36-45 | 46-55 | 56-65 | Prefer not to answer
- 4) What is your highest level of education?
 - Less than a high school degree | High school degree or equivalent [Non-university education beyond high-school (technical college, community college, vocational education) | Some college, no degree | Bachelor's or Associate's degree | Master's degree | Doctoral degree | Prefer not to answer
- 5) Are you a practitioner (researcher, working professional) in Machine Learning?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 6) Please provide your Prolific ID, this is important to get the compensation.